

Unsymmetrically Laminated Composites

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ABSTRACT

Classical lamination theory predicts that the room-temperature shapes of all elevated-temperature cure, unsymmetrically laminated composites are saddles. However, experimental observation indicates that the shapes are often cylindrical. In addition, a second cylinder can sometimes be obtained from the first by a simple snap-through action. A geometrically nonlinear extension to classical lamination theory is used to explain this behavior. Approximate solutions to the nonlinear extension are obtained by using a Rayleigh-Ritz minimization of the laminate's total potential energy. A stability analysis explains the dual cylindrical shapes.

INTRODUCTION

Experimental observation [1] indicates that the room-temperature shape of elevated-temperature cure, unsymmetrically laminated composites do not always conform to the predictions of classical lamination theory [2,3,4]. The classical theory predicts the room-temperature shapes of all unsymmetrically laminated composites to be a saddle. The theory predicts the two principal radii of curvature of the room-temperature shape to be of opposite sign but not necessarily of equal magnitude. Hence, a saddle. Experiments show that, in many cases, unsymmetric laminates have a cylindrical room-temperature shape. This is equivalent to having one principal radius of curvature equal to zero. Whether the saddle or cylindrical shape exists depends somewhat on the inplane dimensions and the thickness of the laminate. In addition to the appearance of the cylindrical shape, oftentimes a laminate can be forced into another cylindrical shape by a snap-through action. The generators of the second cylinder are perpendicular to the generators of the first cylinder. Also, the radius of curvature of the second cylinder is opposite in sign to the radius of curvature of the first cylinder. This sort of behavior is simply not predicted by the classical theory. This paper presents an overview of a theory which explains this behavior. In addition, some interesting numerical results are presented. Experimental data is included to support the theory.

PROBLEM DEFINITION

Before proceeding it is important to define the nomenclature of the problem and the specific problem discussed. A laminate is said to be symmetric if for every lamina at a specific distance to one side of the laminate's geometric mid-plane, there is an identical lamina the same distance on the other side of the geometric midplane. These two lamina must have identical material properties, thickness, and fiber orientation. If these conditions are not met, a laminate is said to be unsymmetric. In this case, there is an elastic coupling between inplane deformations and out-of-plane deflections. The problem of attaining a room-temperature shape, and the apparent deviations from the classical theory, are illustrated in fig. 1. Shown in the figures is the x-y-z coordinate system to be used later to describe the mechanics of unsymmetric laminates. Figure 1a shows a laminate flat at its elevated curing temperature. This configuration exists at the elevated temperature when the laminate is between the heads of a platen press or between caul plates in an autoclave. After curing, the laminate is cooled to room temperature and removed from the press or autoclave. The cooling of the laminate causes inplane thermal deformations. Because of the coupling between inplane deformations and out-of-plane deflections in unsymmetric laminates, an unsymmetric laminate will warp out-of-plane as it cools. Figure 1b shows the room-temperature saddle shape predicted by the classical theory. Figures 1c and 1d show two possible cylindrical shapes, the shapes often observed. One cylinder can be obtained from the other by a snap-through action. Finally, by classical lamination theory is meant a theory which assumes that the Kirchhoff hypothesis is valid for the laminate as-a-whole, that through-the-thickness shear deformations are negligible, that each lamina is linear elastic, that each lamina is in a state of plane stress, and that geometric nonlinearities are negligible. This theory must be modified to explain the behavior of unsymmetric laminates.

APPROACH TO SOLUTION

The key to explaining the thermal deformation behavior of unsymmetric laminates is recognizing that the out-of-plane deflections of the cured laminate are many times the laminate's thickness. Linear plate-like theories are generally valid only if the out-of-plane deflections are limited to be a fraction of the plate thickness. So it is with classical lamination theory. The classical theory assumes the following strain displacement relations:

$$\begin{aligned} e_{11} &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} - z \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}; \\ e_{22} &= \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} - z \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2}; \\ e_{12} &= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} - 2z \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y \partial x} \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

In the above, $u^0(x,y)$ and $v^0(x,y)$ are the displacements of the laminate midplane in the x and y directions. The quantity $w(x,y)$ is the laminate's out-of-plane deflections. The e_{ij} 's are the laminate strains, 1 being associated with the x direction and 2 being associated with the y direction. To cope with the large out-of-plane deflections, the strain-displacement relations have to be modified to include geometric nonlinearities. The von Karman strain measures are appropriate in this case [5]. The strain-displacement relations thus become

$$\begin{aligned} e_{11} &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 - z \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}, \\ e_{22} &= \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 - z \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2}, \\ e_{12} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right) - 2z \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y \partial x} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Using these relations in place of the relations of eq. 1, governing differential equations can be derived for three independent variables u^0 , v^0 , and w . The equations will be nonlinear partial differential equations which in all likelihood cannot be solved. (These equations would be the nonlinear counterpart to eqs. 5.6, 5.7, and 5.8, for example, in [2].) The difficulty in solving the governing equations suggests the obtaining of approximate solutions to the problem. Finite-element or finite-difference solutions are possible but more can be learned about the physics of the problem if the approximate scheme is kept simpler. The approach chosen here is a Rayleigh-Ritz approach to the minimization of the total potential energy. This approach has two distinct advantages. First, it is well known that with even rather crude approximations to the deformation behavior, the Rayleigh-Ritz scheme can lead to quite accurate results. Secondly, and important to the problem at hand, the dual cylinders suggest bi-stable energy states. Thus the whole question of the stability of the predicted solutions needs to be addressed. Energy calculations are a convenient way to assess stability.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The total potential energy of an elastic solid is written as [6],

$$W = \int_{Vol} \left(\frac{1}{2} C_{ijkl} e_{ij} e_{kl} - \beta_{ij} e_{ij} \Delta T \right) dVol - W_{ext}. \quad (3)$$

Here the C_{ijkl} are the material's elastic constants and the β_{ij} are constants related to the elastic constants and the material's coefficients of thermal expansion. The quantity ΔT is the temperature change from the cure temperature to room temperature. The expression W_{ext} is the work done by external tractions on the laminate as it cools to room temperature. The energy at the elevated cure temperature is assumed to be the datum ($W = 0$). All material properties are considered to be independent of temperature.

It is assumed, with a reasonable degree of accuracy, that as the laminate cools to room temperature and attains its final shape, the net work of all external tractions is zero. Thus only the integral remains in eq. 3. Also, because of the much simpler algebra associated with such lay-ups, only cross-ply laminates have been considered to date. With $W_{ext} = 0$ and considering only cross-ply laminates, the total potential energy can be written as

$$W = \int \int \int \left[\frac{1}{2} \bar{Q}_{11} e_{11}^2 + \bar{Q}_{12} e_{11} e_{22} + 2\bar{Q}_{66} e_{12}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \bar{Q}_{22} e_{22}^2 - (\bar{Q}_{11} \alpha_x + \bar{Q}_{12} \alpha_y) e_{11} \Delta T - (\bar{Q}_{12} \alpha_x + \bar{Q}_{22} \alpha_y) e_{22} \Delta T \right] dx dy dz. \quad (4)$$

Because of the plane-stress assumptions inherent in lamination theory, the C_{ijkl} reduce to the reduced stiffnesses \bar{Q}_{ij} . The β_{ij} are related to the reduced stiffnesses and the coefficients of thermal expansion of the laminate in the x and y direction, α_x and α_y . Since only cross-ply laminates are being considered, $\bar{Q}_{16} = \bar{Q}_{26} = \alpha_{xy} = 0$.

The e_{ij} are related to the three components of displacement u^0 , v^0 , and w via eq. 2. To implement the Rayleigh-Ritz procedure, these three components of displacement are approximated by polynomials in x and y . The out-of-plane displacements can adequately be approximated by the following:

$$w = \frac{ax^2}{2} + \frac{by^2}{2}, \quad (5)$$

where a and b are unknown and to-be-determined constants. This choice of approximation is motivated by observation of laminate shapes. With $a > 0$, $b < 0$, the saddle of fig. 1b can be represented. With $a > 0$, $b = 0$, the cylinder of fig. 1c can be approximated, while $a = 0$, $b < 0$ approximates the cylinder of fig. 1d. The approximations for u^0 and v^0 are not as easily constructed. However, much of the u^0 displacement is a rigid body motion. This is due to the curling of the lamina in the x - z plane. Using this and the assumption that for

cross-ply laminates the midplane inplane shear strains are probably zero, the approximation for u^0 takes the form

$$u^0 = cx - \frac{a^2x^3}{6} - \frac{abxy^2}{4} . \quad (6)$$

In this expression c is a to-be-determined constant. With this form of u^0 , the laminate midplane inplane elongation strains are practically independent of spatial location. Similar arguments for the displacement v^0 lead to the approximation

$$v^0 = dx - \frac{b^2y^3}{6} - \frac{abx^2y}{4} . \quad (7)$$

Here d is a to-be-determined constant.

Substituting eqs. 5-7 into eq. 4 leads to an equation of the form

$$W = \int_{z=-h/2}^{h/2} \int_{y=-L_y/2}^{L_y/2} \int_{x=-L_x/2}^{L_x/2} F(a,b,c,d, \bar{Q}_{ij}, \alpha_x, \alpha_y, \Delta T, x, y, z) dx dy dz , \quad (8)$$

where $F(\)$ means 'a function of.' With the limits on the integral it is assumed that at its elevated cure temperature, fig. 1a, the laminate has dimensions L_x by L_y by h . The integral on the right hand side of eq. 8 must be evaluated explicitly and the first and second variation of W with respect to a , b , c , and d determined. This algebra is tedious but straightforward. Integration of the \bar{Q}_{ij} 's with respect to z leads to the familiar A , B , and D matrices of lamination theory. Integration of the \bar{Q}_{ij} 's, α_x , α_y , and ΔT with respect to z leads to the definition of effective inplane thermal forces and moments. These are also the same as the definitions in the classical theory. Integration with respect to x and y leads to terms which reveal the nonlinear aspects of the problem. If $L_x = L_y = 0$, the energy expression is the energy expression associated with classical lamination theory.

With the problem being reduced to finding the four unknowns a , b , c , and d , the first variation of W becomes

$$\delta W = \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial a}\right)\delta a + \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial b}\right)\delta b + \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial c}\right)\delta c + \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial d}\right)\delta d . \quad (9)$$

For the potential energy to be a minimum, δW must be zero. Equation 9 is of the form

$$\delta W = f_1(a, b, c, d)\delta c + f_2(a, b, c, d)\delta b + f_3(a, b, c, d)\delta c + f_4(a, b, c, d)\delta d = 0 . \quad (10)$$

For the first variation of W to be zero,

$$f_i = 0, \quad i = 1, 4 . \quad (11)$$

The f_i are nonlinear algebraic equations involving a , b , c , d , and the geometric and material properties of a laminate. The solution to the four equations is obtained numerically using a Newton-type algorithm. In general, for the laminates considered to date, there is either one real solution to eq. 11 or three real solutions. This will be seen in the next section.

The taking of the first variation of the potential energy only gives the stationary values of the energy. These, of course, are equilibrium states. The concern here is with stable equilibrium states, or minimums in energy. Simitses [7] has looked at stability criteria for discretized systems such as the one here. For the case at hand, the stability of solutions can be determined by examining the 4×4 matrix of partial first derivatives of f_i with respect to a , b , c , and d . If the matrix is positive definite, then the solution to eq. 11 corresponds to stable equilibrium. Thus, for a laminate with a specific stacking sequence, specific geometry, specific material properties, and specific cur-

ing temperature, the numerical solution or solutions, as the case may be, to eq. 11 are found. With each solution, the positive definiteness of the matrix of first partials is assessed. Since the quantities a and b determine the observed shapes, attention is limited to how these quantities are effected by laminate size, laminate thickness, stacking arrangements, etc.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

To examine some of the consequences of the theory and to correlate the predictions of the theory with experimental observation, numerical results are presented for a typical graphite-epoxy.

Figures 2-4 show the predicted room-temperature curvatures of various square ($L_x = L_y = L$) laminates as a function of the laminate's side length. Since experiments seemed to indicate a size effect, both in relation to the laminate's thickness and in relation to the laminate's inplane dimensions, this approach to presenting the numerical results has been adapted.

Figure 2 shows the curvature characteristics of square $[0_2/90_2]_T$ laminates. Figure 2a shows the x-direction curvature, a , as a function of side length while fig. 2b shows the y-direction curvature, b . Note the mirror-image symmetry in the two curvature characteristics. Immediately evident in the figure is the fact that for laminates with side lengths less than 38 mm, the solutions are single valued. This branch of the solution characteristics is denoted as branch AB. For laminates with side lengths greater than 38 mm, the solutions are triple valued. These triple-valued solution branches are denoted as branches BC, BD, and BE. It is important to note the relation between the three branches in figs. 2a and 2b. The stability analysis shows branch BD corresponds to an unstable equilibrium solution. All other branches are stable. The physical interpretation of these solutions is very interesting.

Branch AB corresponds to laminates with saddle shapes at room temperature. The x-direction curvature and the y-direction curvature are equal in magnitude but of opposite sign. The solution for $L = 0$ (point A in the figures) is the prediction of classical lamination theory. Thus, square $[0_2/90_2]_T$ laminates less than 38 mm on a side will be saddle shaped. On the other hand, if the laminate is, say, 200 mm on a side, quite different behavior is exhibited. The laminate can have the shape dictated by branch BC, or the shape dictated by branch BE. Branch BC corresponds to a laminate with a large curvature in the x direction and no curvature in the y direction. This represents a cylinder with generators in the y direction. On the other hand, branch BE corresponds to a laminate with a large (in magnitude) curvature in the y direction and no curvature in the x direction. This represents a cylindrical laminate with generators in the x direction. The theory thus predicts the dual cylindrical shapes so often observed. These dual cylindrical shapes are predicted for laminates with side lengths greater than 75-80 mm. Two experimental measurements are indicated on the figure. These are taken from [1]. Branch BD, the unstable solution, is a continuation of the saddle branch. Thus the shape predicted by the classical theory becomes unstable as laminate size increases. In fact, as laminate size increases from zero, the predicted saddle becomes shallower and shallower relative to the saddle predicted by the classical theory. For laminates between 38 mm and 75-80 mm on a side, two shapes are predicted. However these laminates are more saddle-like the closer the side length is to 38 mm. The range $38 \text{ mm} < L < 75 \text{ mm}$ represents a transition behavior.

Figure 3 shows the shape characteristics of square $[0_4/90_4]$ laminates, laminates twice the thickness of the laminates in fig. 2. Since there is symmetry to the solutions for a and b , only the solution for a is shown. The shape and stability characteristics are similar to the characteristics of the thinner laminates, with an important exception. The side length at which stable saddle shape behavior disappears, point B, is greater, roughly, by a factor of two. Thus the thicker the laminate, the greater the side length can be made before the saddle shape disappears. Based on figs. 2 and 3 and other cases not shown,

it appears that when the side length of $[0_n/90_n]_T$ laminates exceeds the laminate thickness by about a factor of 70, the unique (in the sense of mathematically single-valued) saddle behavior disappears. An experimental measurement from a saddle shaped 63.5 mm x 63.5 mm laminate is indicated on the figure. This is taken from [8].

Finally, fig. 4 shows the shape characteristics of square $[0_3/90]_T$ laminates. These laminates are the same thickness as the laminates in fig. 2 but one lamina is rotated 90° . Figure 4 indicates markedly different behavior. It is important to note the larger horizontal scale and the different vertical scales in figs. 4a and 4b. Finally, note that the numerical values of branch CBD in fig. 4b have been multiplied by 50 before plotting them. Without magnification, this branch would be very close to the horizontal axis.

Noticeably lacking in the behavior of the $[0_3/90]_T$ laminates is the coalescence of the solution branches. The coalescence of solutions as in figs. 2 and 3 is often called bifurcation behavior. The disjoint behavior of fig. 4 is referred to as limit point behavior. Bifurcation is usually associated with the behavior of 'perfect' systems. A $[0_2/90_2]_T$ laminate is 'perfectly antisymmetric.' A $[0_2/90/91]_T$ laminate would exhibit limit point rather than bifurcation behavior. Physically it would be difficult to distinguish the behavior of a $[0_2/90_2]_T$ laminate from the behavior of a $[0_2/90/91]_T$ laminate. Mathematically there is a difference. The stability analysis indicates branch BD represents unstable equilibrium solutions.

Figure 4 indicates that the classical lamination theory predicts a saddle shape with the x-direction curvature much smaller than the y-direction curvature. As laminate size increases, the smaller curvature is suppressed and eventually becomes zero. The larger (in magnitude) curvature remains unaffected. For laminates with side lengths between 50 and 180 mm, the shape is cylindrical. What is important is that there is only one cylindrical shape. There is not another cylindrical shape into which the laminate can be snapped. For side lengths greater than 180 mm, there are two shapes possible. Branch AE continues to be a viable shape. Alternatively, branch BC represents a viable shape. For side lengths between 180 and 400 mm, strictly speaking, one shape is a saddle, the other shape is a cylinder. However, the y-direction curvatures of saddle branch BC between 180 mm and 400 mm are actually quite small and not easily detected. For side lengths greater than 400 mm, the two possible shapes are both definitely cylindrical, one cylinder having much more curvature than the other. No experimental data is available for these laminates.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

It is obvious from the results presented that the room-temperature behavior of unsymmetric laminates is quite different than the behavior predicted by the classical theory. The unorthodox behavior of unsymmetric laminates should be viewed as a positive feature of composite materials which can be put to use. For more details on the behavior of unsymmetric laminates, the reader is encouraged to consult [9,10,11].

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Fig. 3 Curvature Characteristics of Square $[0_4/90_4]_T$ Laminates

Fig. 2 Curvature Characteristics of Square $[0_2/90_2]_T$ Laminates

Fig. 4 Curvature Characteristics of Square $[0_3/90]_T$ Laminates

